

LEISURE IN THE FOCUS OF SOCIAL NETWORKS OF YOUTH OF THE REPUBLIC OF KARAKALPAKSTAN

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***Annotation.** Nowadays, one of the daily leisure activities of young people is social networks. Social networks quickly entered life of most modern people. Involvement and immersion in the virtual space affects many aspects human life: physical and mental health, relationships with other people, self-perception, self-attitude, self-esteem and much more. Of course, these changes could not go unnoticed by many domestic and foreign scientists, which the phenomenon of social networks and the Internet is very popular to study. In this article, the authors provide an overview research on social networks of youth in the Republic of Karakalpakstan. Modern youth leisure is closely connected with the Internet and social networks. Today, only in rare cases can you meet a person who does not have a registered personal page on at least one of the currently popular social networks. Research on social networks and blogs in ethnography is interpreted as digital ethnography or virtual ethnography. "Virtual ethnography" has recently been used to designate a set of methods aimed at studying participants in computer-mediated communication.*

***Keywords:** social networks, Internet, youth, leisure, youth life, subculture.*

INTRODUCTION

Modern youth leisure is closely connected with the Internet and social networks. Today, only in rare cases can you meet a person who does not have a registered personal page on at least one of the currently popular social networks. Research on social networks and blogs in ethnography is interpreted as digital ethnography or virtual ethnography. "Virtual ethnography" has recently been used to designate a set of methods aimed at studying participants in computer-mediated communication [1.p.257]. According to Irina Aleksandrovna Jacob, analysis of social networks is now a popular topic for research at the intersection of anthropology, social anthropology, information theories, social psychology, and social linguistics. One of the pressing problems in modern ethnography and anthropology is social networks and youth blogs. Modern leisure permeates the entire daily life of boys and girls, increasingly acquiring virtual forms. Virtual space provides opportunities to obtain information about possible types of recreation, territories, cultural and leisure institutions, as well as search for information and communication; conditions for self-realization in the leisure sphere have been created in the virtual space.

THE MAIN PART

Before proceeding to the material of interest, one should look at the background, that is: The history of the formation of social networks in the Republic of Uzbekistan and Karakalpakstan. In 1992, the creation of the concern of state telecommunication enterprises "Uzbektelecom" began in Uzbekistan on the basis of regional communications departments of state enterprises of postal and electrical communications. In 2014, Uztelecom carried out the construction of fiber-optic communication lines for broadband access using modern technologies in the sections Buzatau-Kungrad, Guzar-Baysun, Denau-Uzun-Shargun, Jaslik-Karakalpakstan, Muynak- Qibla Ustyurt", "Uzun-Tajikistan Border" with the provision of convergent services such as video telephony,

Internet television, high-speed Internet, viewing HDTV channels and others. And by 2025, 1,138.1 km of fiber-optic communication lines have been laid in rural areas of Uzbekistan and Karakalpakstan (including sparsely populated and hard-to-reach areas), as well as social infrastructure facilities, including medical, local police stations, government bodies, and with the completion of up to 37,344 ports [2.<https://uztelecom.uz/ru/o-kompanii-1/khronika-sobytiy/>].

Along with the development of transport, the spread of telephony, radio, television and e-mail has led to the fact that the concept of distance has become relative. This phenomenon in science is called time-space compression [3.p.7]. Social networks have shown themselves to be a new and sustainable cultural phenomenon, and with increasing popularity in society, they influence it more and more. The "Internet", as a global information system, forms cyberspace, that is, a special reality, which in turn gives rise to "cyberculture" with its own terms, values, and way of thinking. In its designated form, the "Internet network" today is one of the special components of the formation of the information society [4.p.177]. Social networks are online platforms that allow people to create profiles, connect with other users, and share information [5. URL <https://nauchniestati.ru/spravka/soczialnye-seti/> (дата обращения: 08.02.2024)]. As a rule, a participant in these networks registers in the community, creates an account, posts personal information about himself, information about his education, interests, etc. Then he establishes contacts with his friends and acquaintances registered on the network. A network member can join interest groups, exchange messages with other participants, join discussions, post photos, videos, etc. The most popular social networks among young people" in Uzbekistan and the Republic of Karakalpakstan: Telegram, Facebook, Instagram, Whatsapp. Modern youth are active users of social networks, thanks to which they can communicate with residents of different countries and continents, thereby establishing connections between representatives of different cultures. Nowadays, almost all social networks allow you to post your personal blog. Blogs (from English, web log - web log, web protocol); Each participant can keep their own journal - leave entries containing text or multimedia. Blogs are often written in the form of a personal diary [6.p.177]. Other visitors: can leave comments on these posts. The user also has the opportunity to make friends with similar interests, regulate access to records, etc. On the basis of such systems, community journals are created, which are maintained collectively. William Strauss and Neil Howe consider young people as generation "Z": every 20–25 years' people are born whose worldview is not similar to the beliefs of their predecessors. The theory of generations is associated with temporary periods of economic growth in states. Generation Z Years: since 2001 This is the generation of people who are said to have been born with a smartphone in their hands. They are surrounded by gadgets from an early age and understand technology even better. They are well versed in the modern world and surrounding information, follow trends, quickly understand what is interesting and necessary for them, and what is not. Passion for continuous education. This does not mean standard school and university education, but self-education, learning everything new. For example, they are interested in understanding how this or that gadget works, how to shoot and process videos, and how to make money on the Internet.

DISCUSSION

Today, virtual space significantly influences the lives of young people in the Karakalpakstan Republic in the city of Nukus. This is evidenced by the data obtained during the sociological survey and the author's field materials. Analysis of the results of the questionnaire survey on the second block of questions regarding the general activity of young people showed that the majority of respondents noted that they are in the virtual space quite often, i.e. when there

is free time - 51.5%; 30.5% of respondents indicated that they are on the Internet almost always; 18% noted that they log into it quite rarely, only when there is a need, and 0% practically do not use the Internet (Appendices No. 8). Looking at the statistics of the sociological survey, you can see that the most popular virtual network communities among young people in the city of Nukus are "Telegram" used by 65.6%, "Instagram" used by 28.5%, of the respondents 0.8% uses Whatsapp applications, "other" was chosen by 5.1%. (Appendix No. 9). An interesting fact is that no young people were found who do not use social networks. The accessibility of the Internet has led to the fact that young people spend almost all their free time, but also their working time, in the virtual space: looking for information, communicating, organizing leisure time, and the like. And so, what is the attractiveness of the social networks "Telegram", "Instagram", "Whatsapp".

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Summarizing the above, it is necessary to note the following that in the course of research using the sociological method and field materials, the following conclusions can be drawn.

Firstly, urban youth use social networks for their own benefit, work, study, information search, and cultural exchange.

Secondly, the number of people using social networks for entertainment purposes has increased, which could potentially contribute to a decrease in the social activity of young people. The results of our study confirm that social networks are mainly beneficial. And also, as a result of the interpretation of empirical data, it was revealed that the basis of youth communication in virtual network communities are the following motives: knowledge, communication, affiliation, cooperation, recreation, play, self-realization, self-affirmation.

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